

SOLUTRÉ

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Keywords

Economics, Land-use Planning, Natural Heritage, Protected Areas Management, Rural Development, Stakeholder Management, Strategic Decision-making, Sustainability, Territorial Governance, Tourism

Figure 1. Photo of a SOLUTRÉ play session (authors' team). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

SOLUTRÉ (see Figure 1) is an analog board game developed in a French context that explores how a rural area can develop by reconciling local quality of life, tourism development, and a

good ecological status. Thanks to this semi-cooperative game, players can take on the perspective and actions of a territorial actor, aiming to manage the territory while navigating their conflicting interests collectively and sometimes antagonistic sustainability challenges. This game is used in higher education and by professionals in geography and land planning to teach territorial planning and governance, and to encourage students and professionals to consider different paths to sustainable development. It helps students to understand the complexity of a territory by modeling its dynamics. Students can gain a better understanding of these intertwined dynamics and even observe how the territory evolves throughout the game. The game's researchers and authors have been working on this project since 2016. It required four successive research programs to reach this edition. In 2017, territorial diagnostics based on qualitative field surveys enabled the 2017–2018 cohort of the BIOTERRE Master's program to develop a beta version of the game. This version was refined by a game designer starting in 2020. The game's formalization was further refined by a society called PlayTime.

Facts

Release date:	June 2024
Developer:	Anne Jégou, Damien Marage, David Simiand, Nicolas Bécu, Brice Anselme, Laurent Simon, Catherine Carré
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	5–10 (one box – one game table)
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	90 minutes.
Languages:	French, English (Box is in French; English is a Print & Play version)
Environment:	A classical classroom
Material:	No additional material needed
Price:	Print & Play versions are freely available. Board game costs €55 per box.

Resonance & Criticism

Surveys were conducted after the session, one with 268 students and another with 31 planning professionals. The game was very well received: 87% of students and nearly all professionals recommended it.

In 2024, SOLUTRÉ received the Grand Prize from ISAGA (International Simulation and Gaming Association), with the jury recognizing it as a highly accomplished land-planning game.

Two main criticisms emerged. First, the game has been criticized for its weak emphasis on sustainability in territorial development. The relevance of strong sustainability and degrowth can be a key topic in the debriefing session. The second criticism concerns the game's complexity, which makes it less accessible to the public. However, managing territorial

complexity is precisely the game's main learning objective, making SOLUTRÉ particularly relevant for higher education.

Game Principle & Process

SOLUTRÉ requires five players, each of them representing a different role: mayor, inhabitant, tourism professional, conservationist, and wine-grower. In turn, the five players carry out territorial development actions, generating resources, improving hospitality facilities, preserving biodiversity, etc. These actions contribute to both the players' secret objectives and their common objectives. They make decisions, which can be more or less organized. Having a degree of control over each part of the territory, they have some room for maneuver. However, for optimal results, it is in their interest to share or even negotiate around their actions. For example, the inhabitant can set up a health service and several leisure and cultural activities, regulate the influx of tourists by offering bed-and-breakfast accommodation, or increase the appeal to tourists (auditorium, music festival). Of the five players, the inhabitant is the only one with actions that enable them to act directly and alone on brush clearance, eco-pasturing, and volunteer brush clearance.

SOLUTRÉ is highly sensitive to the way facilitators introduce individual and collective objectives to the players. Because the game is designed for learning purposes, determining the winner matters less than debriefing about the players' experience and the implicit content.

Depending on where SOLUTRÉ is played and on the players' expectations, facilitators can present the individual and collective objectives as having the same importance, and let the players accomplish both; they can also make individual success conditional on achieving the common objective (renewing the label); alternately, facilitators can leave this question aside and let the players set their own goals and hierarchies.

SOLUTRÉ is part of the case study sheets of the companion modeling approach: <https://www.commod.org/en/case-studies/solutre>. Our observation sheet and questionnaires are also directly inspired by the Serious Games Observation Manual. To develop the game, an ARDI diagram (Actors, Resources, Dynamics, Interactions), derived from the Commod methodology (Etienne, 2010), was formalized to model the territorial dynamics of the Grand Site de France Solutré-Pouilly-Vergisson.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

SOLUTRÉ is primarily a geography and planning game, but it is also relevant to a wide range of disciplines, including ecology, economics, and the humanities. It can be played by both students and planning professionals. Its main learning objective is to help players understand the conflicting issues involved in the sustainable management of a heritage territory.

More specifically, SOLUTRÉ allows players to experience the complexity of territorial governance by taking on the role of a local stakeholder. Students not only gain insight into the dynamics between stakeholders in land-use planning, but they also have the opportunity to position themselves, collaborate, and develop strategies. Through the game, they experiment with power relations among local actors and engage in the collective resolution of territorial issues.

Players are particularly invited to navigate the balance between personal strategies and collective decision-making, often through moral dilemmas. The debriefing session provides an opportunity to reflect on and discuss the sustainability model represented in the game.

In surveys, students highlighted the acquisition of soft skills. Playing SOLUTRÉ enables them to engage in collective intelligence, applying their negotiation skills, persuasive abilities, initiative, patience, and capacity for compromise. They also gain experience in collective decision-making within a complex environment.

Facilitating a game session is highly flexible: it can be adapted to different educational objectives and requires varying levels of preparation. Numerous resources are available on the website. One teacher can oversee up to four gaming tables simultaneously for a group of approximately 35 students.

Effectiveness

Based on 268 respondents, survey results indicate that the game is a success. Professionals rated their enjoyment at 8.3/10, while students rated it at 7.5, highlighting a well-balanced game flow. The enthusiasm among professionals can also be seen as validation of the knowledge embedded in the game. Over 82% of students would like to play the session again. Over 87% of them would recommend the game to their colleagues or friends (Marage et al., 2024).

Less than 38% of students feel they avoid academic work. However, more than 73% of them have learned about governance and regional and urban planning. A discourse analysis was conducted. Students valued cross-disciplinary skills such as dialogue, listening, and negotiation. However, very few mentioned the moral dilemma and sustainable development. The lexical field of the economy, development, attractiveness, and tourism is much broader than that of the environment and nature conservation. Starting from the simulated reality, the game appears to represent a weak sustainability model linked to the Anthropocene era. Gameplay and debriefing allow for critiquing weak sustainability and help students and their teachers grasp the moral dilemmas and critical engagement that arise.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

SOLUTRÉ does not present any significant problematic aspects, as it is semi-cooperative and does not involve violent scenarios. As a board game, it does not contain any hazardous

situations. Players with disabilities can participate by playing in pairs or receiving assistance from a teammate. The graphics have been designed to accommodate color blind players, though they are less optimized for those with myopia.

However, SOLUTRÉ is not particularly gender-inclusive, despite the creators' efforts to avoid masculine biases in stakeholder names and objectives. Overall, the game remains well-suited for higher education students.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

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